

Dance in Open and Distance Learning: Findings from Needs Assessment Study in India

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Abstract: *The objectives of this study were two fold - to assess the demand for programmes on Dance through ODL and to identify major content to be covered under the programme. The present study projects the need for programmes on dance with which it is felt that the interests and needs of the student community would be addressed. The study was undertaken following a survey research through questionnaire, and data was collected from 121 respondents. The key survey questions focused on: need and relevance of the level of programme and possibilities for other such advanced learning programmes on ODL; basic eligibility requirements; suggested broad contents of the programme pertaining to electives; ratio of practical and theory division; job prospects; details of such programmes on offer elsewhere; willingness to join the programme; probability of support for enrolment from individuals; preference amongst different levels of programme. The results revealed that, majority of respondents felt the need for a one-year diploma level ODL programme in dance followed by graduate and postgraduate programmes too. The important career prospects perceived by respondents include: employment in dance troupes, schools, cultural institutes; and self employment. The important content areas with regard to electives suggested by the respondents include: specialization in Bharatanatayam, followed by dance forms Kucipudi/ Kathak, Chhau dance, regionspecific folk and tribal dance forms and Kalarippayattu martial arts as one of the secondary courses. In the light of the findings of the study and related discussion, it is recommended to develop diploma programme on dance in ODL to begin with and subsequently develop bachelor's and master's programmes in dance. This would meet the education needs of various stakeholders in the professional performance, cultural and art related sector.*

Keywords: *Need assessment in dance, Open and distance learning, Dance education, Indian classical and folk dances*

Introduction

Indian dance forms bring out the quintessential cultural ethos of the regions they originate from. From the exuberant beats of Bhangra, the effervescent undulations in Manipuri, valorous strides of Chhau dancers or the flamboyant *netra-abhinaya*

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of koodiyattom, to the scintillating *Thillana* of Bharatanatyam, our country has it all. We have inherited a culture that has at its centre, the primary motive of holistic wellbeing of the individual and the community at large and our dance traditions are living examples of continuation of this endeavour. To experience the richness of our precious dance forms as traditional gifts is one thing, to nurture them and provide them the much needed impetus for sustenance and continuation amongst a new generation is another. From the sole teaching-learning delivery mechanism of Guru-shishya parampara, today's scene unfolds to have technology based delivery where the modern guru can reach out to the shishya in their living rooms. Surprisingly, education in the field of dance in India has been rather slow to come into the ambit of the colleges and universities. However, as new horizons are explored, challenges abound.

Training in artistic skills is essential for holistic development of each and every human being. Apart from addressing its core concern of developing skilled performers in arts and allied areas, this has become part of life-skill education in school curriculum. A study by Stanford University and the Carnegie foundation for the advancement of teaching reports that young people who learn the rigors of planning and production in the arts will be valuable employees in the idea-driven work place of the future (see https://wdr.doleta.gov/opr/FULLTEXT/1999_35.pdf). So much so that the University from 2006 onwards has made one creative practice class mandatory curricular requirement in order to graduate. It thus becomes a prime responsibility of educators in the field of dance, to take measures to reach out and promote the learning of dance- be it classical or folk or tribal dance forms with an objective of not just performance training but to educate through dance. It empowers equally a child and an adult regardless of physical capabilities, to be expressive in a non-verbal manner and more so, as educationist Susan R. Koff (2000) points out, – to explore and incorporate the physical self as a functioning part of the whole social being. The two poles in the aims of dance education, according to Smith-Autard (2002), are developing dance technical skills on the one hand (acquisition/training of the techniques, dance literacy) and developing creativity (individuality, subjectivity and feelings) on the other. The traditional dance teaching methodology prevalent in India addresses the former to a large extent. This coupled with pedagogical tools to deliver and assess with equal emphasis on using creative process within a structured learning environment would deal with self-regulation and reflection skills, as Soot and Viskus (2014) state that are becoming increasingly important in dance education today.

The School of Performing and Visual Arts at IGNOU has been offering a six-months Certificate in Bharatanatyam since 2010, the response to which has not been very encouraging. The present study projects the need for other programs on dance with which it is felt that the interests and needs of the student community would be addressed. Moreover, as discussed above, apart from very few dance forms like Bharatanatyam that can be offered at many places in India, the same may not

be true for other forms/styles of dance which can be offered only at some places with respect to their need. With these concerns in mind, and considering the wide reach of IGNOU and the viability of ODL mode, a survey was conducted to assess the needs of programmes in Dance especially with reference to diploma with the following objectives:

- To assess the demand for programmes on Dance through ODL.
- To identify major content to be covered under the programme through ODL

Traditional and Institution Based Training of Dance in India

Indian classical dance forms, till 300 years ago, had been preserved and nourished by a set of exclusive class of people who were entrusted with continuance of this heritage. In the early 1900's during the pre-independence, when India had started engaging in a process of 'reviving' its own indigenous cultures, there arose a few institutions that began to patronize the process of teaching-learning of these art forms and thus began the shift from community based guru-shishya learning pattern to a more democratized institutionalization of dance.

In 1927, poet Vallathol Narayana Menon started Kerala Kalamandalam and subsequently, Rukmini Devi Arundale, with the support of Theosophical Society founded the International Centre for Arts, later named as Kalakshetra in the year 1936. In 1938, Uday Shankar started his dance institution at Almora. These cultural institutions eventually became nationally recognized for their effective pedagogy in teaching art forms like dance and music. They followed the Guru-Shishya parampara to a certain extent and patronized the process of teaching-learning of art forms. When college and university education spread in the post-independent India, education with respect to dance took a back seat. Dance education has not responded much to the changing norms of the society nor has it adapted itself to face the future where learning traditional dance just as a passion or propagation of an age old culture in itself are not enough to nourish a dance form or its pedagogical practice. This is where the expertise and resources available with a college/ university helps in development of a traditional subject area like dance. If we take the case of regional forms as in folk and tribal Indian dance forms, they have been an inherent part of cultural festivities, rituals or important family occasions. They are intangible traditions that have been passed from generation to generation without much involvement of institutionalized training and have remained mostly at rural areas. Other than a *Nattupura kalaigal* (folk arts) programme offered in Government Music and Dance college, Tanjavur and Central Sangeet Natak Akademi's special centres for Chhau in Chandankiyari, Bokaro, Koodiyattom in Trivandrum and Manipuri and Thangta in Imphal offer practical oriented courses in different dance forms. As educators with social responsibility, it thus becomes imperative to offer training in these forms and open their scope of learning and performance to a larger group.

Need and Relevance of ODL Programme in Dance

With regard to acquiring /learning a professional skill like dancing or singing, it is a customary practice in India, for a child to be initiated into learning from a tender age of four or five. The child gradually learns the form, picks up the nuances and builds up his/her performance skills coupled with some theoretical knowledge by the age of ten or twelve. Apparently, such a scenario is where the culture of prior learning is prevalent. It rather undermines the relevance of basic programmes like Certificate and Diploma offered by a university with regard to entry level qualifications which is mostly for secondary school pass outs and an age of entry generally allowed for 15 years and above. However, programmes on dance through ODL definitely have its advantages too due to its inbuilt flexibility.

The primary motives of this programme are :-

- skill training,
- creating employment opportunities, and
- vertical mobility in higher education.

It would address a diverse clientele group and their specific needs, for example.

- a) For the prior learners - it recognizes, accredits and builds upon their earlier skill training.
- b) For fresh learners - it imparts training in skill development within a pedagogical frame with emphasis on providing an holistic knowledge base.
- c) For adult learners - it gives scope to learn, perform and fulfill their inherent passion of learning dance.

At present, there are colleges and universities that offer full-time certificate and diploma programmes in dance. Also many private dance institutes run by dancers help their students acquire various certifications given by private bodies like Pracheen kalakendra, Chandigarh and Prayag sangeet samiti, Allahabad, etc,. In such a scenario, the proposed Diploma programme in dance on ODL mode stands to gain from the advantages of the ODL system itself and more importantly IGNOU's national stature. The practical counselling schedules of IGNOU offered at regular intervals encourages phase by phase learning thereby upholding the training methodology necessary for any dance skill to be acquired and mastered. This will be the highlight and advantage of the Diploma programme.

The proposed Diploma programme in dance will be formulated so as to provide the learners with expertise in practical aspects of performance augmented with theoretical inputs of dance. A programme in dance of this kind at the undergraduate level is necessitated by the fact that it would provide a stepping stone for learners to take up dance as a subject in higher education, as a platform for holistic development of professional dancers and also find employment in allied areas.

Methods

Study Design and Instrument

The study was undertaken following a survey research conducted through questionnaire. The questionnaire consisted of the items dealing with: Need and relevance of the level of programme on ODL; basic eligibility requirements; suggested broad contents of the programme pertaining to electives; ratio of practical & theory division; job prospects; details of such programmes on offer elsewhere; willingness to join the programme; probability of support for enrolment from individuals; preference amongst different levels of programme.

As the Diploma programme in Dance would entail basic practical lessons for fundamental skill development in Dance, content based questions related only to specializations. Hence, a basic questionnaire was put to both experts and students. Further, their opinions were sought through open-ended short answer questions. Through this, the student's choice of specialization and the expert's suggested dance forms were derived.

Sampling and Data Collection

Survey was conducted online through email and WhatsApp. This method was chosen to replace the way of eliciting responses by post which was followed earlier. With a questionnaire prepared on Google Forms and its invitations sent on email and WhatsApp, it took around two months to receive the requisite number of responses after which further entries were disallowed. However surprisingly, with help from dancer community and also general audience, 121 responses could be garnered among which, 56 comprised of potential learners who wanted to join the course.

Data Analysis

The data were analyzed using simple frequency and percentages. The responses that were automatically summarized and analyzed by the online software itself showed as pie-charts and bar graphs. For those with customized short answers like course contents, data was documented and analyzed using excel sheet and the documented details are presented as annexures.

Results and Discussion

1. Need and relevance of level of the programme and enrollment willingness

The data revealed that 91.7 percent (112) of the respondents identified the need for diploma in dance as the next level of training after certificate and only 8.3 percent (10) felt it was not so. Other levels in which further training in dance was found necessary were post diploma (26.2 percent); bachelors in performing arts (32 percent); post graduate diploma (20.5 percent); masters (27percent). However a whopping 67.2 percent suggested that programmes in dance should be available at all levels. (Figure-1)

At what other levels do you think there is need for further training in Dance

Figure 1: Other suggested programme levels for dance in ODL

Effectively, 56 respondents turned out to be potential learners whereas 93 of them comprising of experts and members of open pool volunteered to encourage others to join the diploma in dance and other programmes .

2. Entry qualification, medium and career prospects in dance

The results (Figure-2) revealed that 52.1 percent of respondents suggested the entry qualification as 10th pass (63) followed by 12th pass (47.9 percent; 59).

What do you think can be the eligibility for Diploma?

121 responses

Figure 2: Eligibility for Diploma in Dance

With 97.3 percent agreeing that diploma and higher level programmes in dance would provide them employment opportunities, only 2.5 percent felt that it would not do so. Vertical mobility in higher education (15.7 percent); Self employment (38 percent); freelance work in dance troupes (34.7 percent) were career prospects in dance as perceived by the respondents, though 65.3 percent agreed that all of the above areas were viable options available after completion of the programme. (Figure.3). Majority of them agreed that programmes on dance would help them gain employment both as entrepreneurs, employees or freelancers and one third felt that it would be a step for further studies. The medium of English was suggested along with translations in regional languages according to suggested language concerned with dance specialization.

What do you think are job/career prospects for Diploma and higher level programmes

121 responses

Figure 3: Career prospects in dance

3. Practical: Theory ratio

Majority of respondents (95; 77.7 percent) suggested that practical component should be more than 70percent. Among them, 11.6 percent (14) of respondents suggested having 90 percent practical's and 66.1 percent (80) suggested 70 percentage weightage; followed by 50 percent (23; 19 percent) and less than 50 percent (4; 3.3 percent). Only 22.3 percent (27) opined for a practical weightage of 50 percent and lesser. (Figure.4)

Figure 4: Suggested weightage of Practical: Theory

4. Suggested course contents

The respondents of the study made several suggestions about the course contents for diploma in dance. Majority of them (82; 67.2 percent) suggested the inclusion of popular classical dance forms as options to be available as specialized courses in the programme. The frequency* recorded of classical dance forms as specialized courses in practical's is presented as figure 5. Majority respondents suggested practical specialization in Bharatanatyam (146) followed by Kuchipudi (72) then Kathak (64); Odissi (53); Mohiniattom and Kathakali each (52); Manipuri (49); Sattriya (45); Koodiyattom (32).

Figure 5: Suggested course contents (specialized courses- classical forms) to meet the requirements of stakeholders

* Multiple responses

At the same time, a whopping 85 percent (103) suggested inclusion of Folk/ tribal dance forms as specialized courses (Figure 6). Cluster of these forms depending on the area/ state of origin and demand were suggested to be clubbed as options to be delivered at respective area of demand to meet the requirements of the clientele.

Do you think Regional dances like folk and tribal forms can also be offered as specialisation at their respective regions under groupings like for example: Regional dance forms of Tamilnadu/Punjab or likewise

Figure 6: Suggested need and mode of inclusion of regional dance forms as course contents

Majority of respondents (103; 90 percent) made suggestions for inclusion of specialized courses in folk, allied dance and martial art forms to be offered in diploma in dance whereas only 15 percent denied such a possibility. The respondents from all over India voluntarily suggested the need for a range of dance forms both from their region and from other regions too. The order of frequency of their most repeated dance forms is given below (Figure.7).

The most repeated suggestion (20; 17 percent) was for *Chhau*, a semi-classical tribal martial dance of Seraikela, Purulia and Mayurbhanj, which in 2010, was recognized as an important intangible cultural heritage of humanity by the UNESCO. This was followed by *Kalaripayattu*, (14 ; 12 percent) a martial art from Kerala. The regional dance forms suggested were clustered under heads: Bihu, NE dances and dance forms of Gujarat and Rajasthan (16; 14 percent each); regional dance forms of Tamil Nadu, Kerala and Punjab (10; 8 and 9 percent each) (Box-1)

Figure 7: Suggested course contents of regional dance forms (Folk/ semi-classical/ tribal/allied) to meet the requirements of stakeholders

The following specific regional dance forms were suggested as course content. They have been analyzed and clubbed under the respective state of origin except the art forms of Chhau and Kalaripayattu

Box-1: Suggested inclusion of specialized courses that can be clustered under different State heads

- Garba, Dandiya and Ras (Gujarat)
- Ghoomer, Kalbeliya (Rajasthan)
- Pinnal kolattam, Karagattam, Oyilattam, Kummi, Mayilattam, Poikal kuthirai, Kolattam, etc.(Tamil Nadu)
- Teyyam, Ottanthullal, Seethankanthullal, Chakkiarkoothu, Porattukali, Thiruvathirakkali, Kolkali (Kerala)
- Gidda, Bhangra (Punjab)
- Sambhalpuri, Gotipua, Santhal, Gaudiya Nrithya, Rabindra nrithya, lavani, Rouf, Dollu, Yakshagana, Vilasini Natyam, Perini Natyam. (from states of Maharashtra, Jammu & Kashmir, Andhra, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh)

5. Details of similar programmes conducted elsewhere and preference for the level of programme

More than half of the respondents (69; 54.5 percent) were unaware of such programmes in dance being offered elsewhere. However, 52 of those who knew gave a list of such programmes. It was found that apart from only a couple of state universities like Annamalai University, Chidambaram and Potti Sriramulu Telugu University, Hyderabad, that offer 3 year Diploma in Bharatanatyam/ Kuchipudi in distance mode , others like Banaras Hindu University , REVA University, Kalakshetra, Chennai and Tamil university, Tanjavur offer Diploma in Bharatanatyam/ Kathak on regular mode for a duration ranging from 1-4 years. Majority of the respondents rated the need for different levels between a scale of 1 to 5 with preference for Diploma suggested as one with more (42) highest preference scale followed by Masters (27) and then Bachelors (21) (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Scales of preference for different programmes

Conclusion

The study has revealed that there is a strong need for an academic programme on dance on ODL in diploma and higher levels with positive implications for all stakeholders in the art and cultural sector. If an ODL programme on Indian dance forms is made available, the learners after completing the programme will be fully equipped to serve as entrepreneurs, employees or freelancers in cultural and art related areas.

In light of the findings of this study, it is recommended to develop an ODL programme on dance at diploma level followed by other levels with the following objectives:

- To provide a holistic knowledge base of the Indian dance forms vis-à-vis their socio-cultural context.
- To create a foundational understanding of theory, both from texts and traditions.
- To impart basic technical skills in performance of nritta and abhinaya.
- To acquaint the learner with fundamental knowledge of tala and rhythm.
- To develop a creative and analytical outlook and enable project submission
- To help build strong skill base that will pave way for opportunities for performance and advanced learning.

The following broad structure for the programme is suggested:

- Level of programme: Diploma in Dance with inclusion of specialized courses as options in electives (classical and regional dance forms $\frac{3}{4}$ Bharatanatyam, Kuchipudi/Kathak/ Mohiniattom and Chhau to start with).
- Medium of instruction: English to start with (the programme can be translated in to Hindi and regional languages based on need)
- Number of credits: 32 - About 3 major practical courses (16 credits) including a classroom production work, 2 minor general dance theory courses (12 credits) and one Project work (4 credits).
- Admission criterion: 12th pass/equivalent (no upper age limit). An additional criterion would recognize prior training/learning experience and grants exemption with regard to undertaking practical courses. This can be allowed with a formal assessment/certification from a recognized academic institution or professional body with due fulfillment of the learning outcomes for the chosen courses as delineated by the university. However, all students will have to appear and pass assessment tests conducted under university rules.
- Duration of the programme: Minimum 1 year and Maximum 4 years.

Considering the demand as per this study for inclusion of a specialized course on traditional martial art form like Kalarippayattu, it is recommended to be developed as one of the practical courses subsequently in advanced level programme in dance like bachelors or masters.

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